

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

AXIOM OF CARING FOR WELL-BEING OF HUMANITY LIES IN SALVATION OF HUMANITY FROM THE SIN

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Abstract

No matter how many reforms, theories, concepts, proofs, arguments, practical examples we should consider, it is undeniable that axiom of caring for well-being of humanity lies in the salvation of humanity from sin.

Keywords: Mankind, well-being, economic, scientific-technical progress

At the turn of the XX-XXI centuries, humanity is facing new challenges and demands.

It is worth noting that the main reason for overcoming all problems is the survival of humanity and care for their well-being. Therefore, the greatest responsibility rests on the correct and rational management and functioning of the "economy".

Unfortunately, in the civilized and economically developed countries of the modern world, in the officially accepted economic theories and practical economic management activities, the Lord, the principles of the Christian faith and moral norms are almost completely neglected.

Mankind (human) is the only subject in the world created for perfection, which God created in His own image and according to His likeness: "and God blessed them, and God said unto them, "Be fruitful and multiply, and replenish the earth, and subdue it; and have dominion over the fish of the sea, and over the fowl of the air, and over every living thing that moveth upon the earth." (Genesis 1,27-28).

Therefore, taking care of the well-being of the "phenomenon" created for perfection requires great responsibility, caution, intelligence and great spirituality. It is not correct to create only material wealth and best social conditions for the society, maximum satisfaction of their demands and it is enough to say that their well-being is ensured.

Today, when society has reached the highest peak of civilization with its "invaluable" rudens, taking care of their well-being remains an urgent problem. Reduced costs and increased profits through scientific and technical progress another new question has arisen: In particular, have welfare and trends of caring it increased or decreased? Is it still relevant to search for ways to solve it and to develop overcome methods for humanity, or has it become passive?

We will not be morally correct if we do not mention the great role and importance of the achievements of scientific and technical progress in improving the living conditions of mankind, raising their level and well-being. It can be said with confidence that its result is an increase in the life expectancy of the population, a decrease in mental and physical workload. But the main thing is not how much

the process lightens a person's burden, but how the lightening of the burden affects his spiritual mental thinking. Is there a place for a person to realize a clear mind, or does he do everything through conditioned reflexes. "Happy is the man who finds wisdom, And the man who gains understanding; For her proceeds are better than the profits of silver, And her gain than fine gold". (Proverbs 3:13-14)

As we know, scientific and technical progress is seriously affected by globalization and integration processes, which are the main source of modern public relations. In their background, it seems that living conditions are improving and perfecting, but the general economic situation around the world is becoming difficult. Relations between states and individuals are becoming complicated, the presence of unruly economic elements is observed. The growth of globalization and integration processes in general and scientific-technical progress in particular has accelerated the growth of unsustainable, unmanageable economic processes in the world. It is observed that similar economic models are used by different countries, without considering any traditional interests, which is followed as if by identification of models of economic systems of the state, which intensifies the competitive struggle in the market and causes a desire for monopolistic or oligopolistic tendencies. The latter ends with chaos, the proliferation of the shadow economic elements to capture the market, economic and financial crises that affect the population. The socially vulnerable layer has increased, the number of unemployed has increased, the pressure directed at each other by people has increased (expansion), Because of this, the number of mentally, physically, morally and socially damaged population has increased, in balancing of which only economic laws and regularities are powerless. „Envy captured the uneducated nation“. Therefore, the quantitative side is not of decisive importance for achieving the result, but the qualitative side is given priority. We learn about this from the Holy Scriptures. "Then Elijah said, "I'm the only prophet of GOD left in Israel; and there are 450 prophets of Baal. Let the Baal prophets bring up two oxen; let them pick one, butcher it, and lay it out on an altar on firewood—but don't ignite it. I'll take the other ox, cut it up, and

lay it on the wood. But neither will I light the fire... O Baal, answer us! But there was no reply of any kind. Then they danced, hobbling around the altar they had made... altar of the LORD that was broken down. And Elijah took twelve stones, according to the number of the tribes of the sons of Jacob, unto whom the word of the LORD came, saying, Israel shall be thy name... And the water ran round about the altar; and he filled the trench also with water." (B.C. Testament, Third Kings 18,22-45)

Humanity has to wrestle with wolf laws and fight for existence, fight for survival. ⚔ Everything they do on earth is done by processes that are considered unnatural. Humanity cannot or does not use the world as it was given. The country was given to man as "food", as a means of life, but life must first of all be a relationship with God. The world and food were created for human so that they could have a connection with God through them. Only food taken for God's sake could be life-giving. The infinite tragedy of Adam (mankind) is that he perceived food as "life in itself". i.e. He believed in food, when the only object of faith and hope is God. "They have mouths but cannot speak, and eyes but cannot see. They have ears but cannot hear, and noses but cannot smell." (Psalms: 113,13,14,15) They forget that the Creator of the universe is God: "The earth is the LORD's, and all its fullness, The world and those who dwell therein." (Psalms: 23,1-2). For the salvation of humanity, the "Bible" written by people enlightened by God's grace is the head of the main source from which all sciences, including economics, should be fed. That the Bible is a book about the world and man, about humanity and its future, about its ultimate destiny, about its daily existence. "Man - the crown of the supreme of all creation" is not just fancy words. The main focus of Scripture is on humanity, God makes connection with him who bears his image and is called to receive the likeness (deification theosis) connection between God and man, between God and people, between God and humanity... connection is always two-sided.

The fact, which is unfortunately real, clearly tells us that a part of humanity is trying to adapt to the management of the world through the use of unnatural rules. Surround anomalous methods to society and make them consider as natural phenomena and regularities. Fast-paced civilization, acceleration of the scientific-technical process, internationalization, intensified migration processes, free movement of foreign capital, acceleration of the pace of globalization, obviously made it more difficult, expensive and dangerous to take care of the well-being of humanity on earth and highlight its positive results, including their safety. So what's going on? Is it only the weakness of economic science, or the result of the imperfection of economic science in general?

Today the world is facing a common dilemma. This dilemma is the big cross that all humanity has to carry, that the Lord gives us this cross, and sometimes its carrying is heavy and sometimes it is lightened (depending on the spiritual condition of the person). However, this does not mean that humanity does not participate in the creation of its cross, the vertical of

which is the spiritual connection with the Lord, and the horizontal is the spiritual connection with other people. In this way, humanity should create two spiritual pillars, which include: striving for God and striving for neighbor. The apostle Paul says: Bear one another's burdens and thus you will fulfill the law of Christ. "The Lord remind us, humanity: "Come to me, all you who are weary and burdened, and I will give you rest. Take my yoke upon you and learn from me, for I am gentle and humble in heart, and you will find rest for your souls. For my yoke is easy and my burden is light." (Matthew 11,28,29,30)

Globalization is a natural process, how global the economy is, what stage of globalization the earth is in, is also a result of this natural process. "Globalization is an inevitable event and is connected with the development of scientific and technical progress. It can be said that the whole world has become global, but this does not necessarily mean that big countries have to absorb small countries."

Some people think that the spiritual or national values of small nations create conflict and confrontation, which may turn into enmity and strife. In fact, this is not the case at all. These values, their diversity, on the contrary, enrich the world, eliminate conflict and confrontation. However, at the same time, it is necessary to form a moral axis of human values that will promote dialogue between civilizations. The main thing is that in the current of modern processes, we should understand well where the subject is and where the object is. The object is very often nations, and the subject tries to wrap his ideas around that object and remove the national-moral, spiritual achievements, values, which is very dangerous for us. We need to know what is acceptable and what is not, what is pseudoculture.

Today, as political scientists point out, the tragedy that took place in the USA on September 11, 2001 announced to the world the beginning of a new, unprecedented post-modern era in the history of mankind, which requires a fundamental revision of the centuries-old relations between states and peoples. It seems paradoxical, but the stronger the state is from an economic or military point of view, the greater the threat posed by international terrorism, which can attack nuclear power plants, chemical plants, secret laboratories and other important facilities. It is from the point of view of this global common threat and world-scale international cooperation that all problems that prevent the cooperation of states and people's well-being, stability of development should be reviewed. This is the only reasonable alternative to the new reality created in the world. From a geopolitical point of view, the modern system of international relations is based on rivalry not between nation-states, but between nation-empires. This will be one of the most important characteristics of our life, which can be called the most modern. A period where a part of degraded humanity tries to adapt to the world using wrong, unnatural methods and offers it to us in a natural format.

Based on all of the above, we come to one conclusion, which allows us to make a reasonably well-thought-out mix, that:

1. All these problems cannot be solved only by means of economic factors. It is necessary to develop a synergistic social economy.

2. It is not enough and perfect to have a planar perception of the created problem, where the cutoff system is the point of intersection of the axes of the coordinate plane, if this problem is not discussed in the spatial perspective, where the Supreme Lord is, and the cutoff point is the justice.

3. It is not correct to idolize wealth and profit as the main means of satisfying the needs of humanity, unless the main thing is understood that „and also everyone to whom God has given wealth and possessions, and given him power to enjoy them, and to receive his reward and to rejoice in his labor-this is the gift of God.“ (Ecclesiastes: 5,18)

4. It should not be understood that the Christian faith condemns wealth and the rich man. The result of human economic activity is expressed in the creation-accumulation of material wealth and money, and up to that point it is stated in the Law of Great Justice: "We should not belittle the wealth acquired by righteousness and spent in good deeds." And not as it happens today: "Aid to a foreign country today is money paid by the poor in a rich country and received by the rich in a poor country."

5. It is not enough to recognize that properly formulated economic theories and factors can account for the "making of bread" of human existence, unless it is taken into account that "Moses has not given you the bread from heaven, but My Father gives you the true bread from heaven. (John: 6,32)

„It is written and forever remains written, 'Man shall not live by bread alone, but by every word that comes out of the mouth of God.'“ (Matthew: 4,4)

6. Only the recognition that it is necessary to develop the theological-economic principles is not enough for the perfect solution of this problem, if it is not taken into account to which period of human government the vector of this problem leads. What is needed to fix this and why? Therefore, we come to the conclusion that the current situation requires fundamental study, analysis and implementation of certain experiences and views of that time. We have in mind the period of the rule of the judges to show the present and future generations that the main political, economic, social power and strength of mankind is a strong religious feeling, fear, love of the Lord and modesty to Him, which led to the recognition of the theocratic period as the period of ideal governance in human history.

And finally, no matter how many reforms, theories, concepts, proofs, arguments, practical examples we should consider, it is undeniable that axiom of caring for well-being of humanity lies in salvation of humanity from the sin.

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